

Validating the measures of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture in the Context of Administrative and Academic Heads of Selected Public Universities in Uganda

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KEYWORDS: Artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, underlying assumptions, organisational culture.
ABSTRACT: This study analyzes the effect of price perceptions and personal values, underlying assumptions, organisational selling on The study validated the measures of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture in the context of administrative and academic heads of selected public universities in Uganda.

Basing on the conceptualization by Schein (1998), Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture was studied in terms of: artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions. The study used a correlational research design on a sample of 231 respondents that were university managers, namely administrative and academic heads of Kyambogo University (85), 60 for MUST, 63 for Gulu University and 62 people for Busitema University in Uganda. Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire and analysed using quantitative methods that were descriptive and partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) with the help of SmartPLS to determine the measures of Schein's Theory of organisational culture.

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Descriptive results indicated that three constructs of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture of artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, basic underlying assumptions were high. PLS-SEM indicated that the three constructs of artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions were appropriate measures of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture. It was concluded that managers of public universities in Uganda need to promote a high level artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions among administrative and academic heads of departments. Therefore, the study recommended that managers of public universities in Uganda should emphasise artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions among administrative and academic heads of departments.

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INTRODUCTION

Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture advanced by Schein (1985, 1998, 2002, 2004) which explains the relationship between organisational culture elements, is based on ideas put forward by Schein (1983) who proposed three organisational culture levels that must be possessed by effective organisations namely; artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions. However, Hatch (1993) advanced Schein's theory by introducing the cultural dynamics theory that included symbols as a fourth element and further reformulated Schein's theory in terms of dynamism which explains the relationships between cultural elements as processes thereby proposing that culture be constituted by; manifestation, realization, symbolization, and interpretation processes that relate the four cultural elements. On their part, O'Reilly et al. (1991) identified seven profiles, such as innovation, stability, respect for people, outcome orientation, attention, team, and aggression which were in line with the three levels of Schein's Organisational Culture Theory. In the same vein, O'Reilly et al. (1991) Organisational Culture Profile was revised by Sarros et al. (2005) in terms of different thematic areas: people, business, environmental, adaptation, consistency, mission, and involvement cultures (Bogala & Debela, 2024).

Resultantly, Groysberg et al. (2018) maintained Schein's culture elements and went ahead to introduce an organisational cultural style that involved; caring, purpose, learning, enjoyment, results, authority, safety and order; and categorized cultures as either stable, emphasizing authority, order, consistency, predictability, and the status quo, or flexible, characterized by adaptability, openness to change, learning, creativity, and innovation. Relatedly, Bogale and Debela (2024) studied organisational culture using the organisational culture assessment instrument (OCAI) framework which specified four main types of culture in terms of; clan, market, adhocracy, and hierarchy typologies. The basics of the OCAI were extracted from the 'competing values Framework' which was a product of Cameron and Quinn (2006). Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture helps to explain how organisational culture influences employees' job success in any organisation and thereby positively influencing organisational innovation, productivity and ultimately effectiveness.

Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture states that organisational culture is the pattern of basic assumptions which a given group has invented, discovered, or developed in learning to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, which have worked well enough to be considered valid, and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems (Schein, 1983). This implies inducting new members into the existing belief system of the organisation so that uniformity and stability exist that foster organisational effectiveness. This is due to the fact that organisational culture is a group attitude that progresses over time and proves unyielding to modification once entrenched (Hardcopf et al., 2021), significantly influence interpersonal relationships, behaviours, and communication among employees during day-to-day work (Akhavan et al., 2014), and consequently emerges as a key organisational feature and situational aspect, exhibiting potential stability or flexibility that permeates all facets and activities of the organisation..

Schein (1983) first developed four main attributes of organisational culture that influence organisational effectiveness that are structural stability, depth, breadth, and patterning/integration which yield to three major competencies of; stability, consistency, and meaning (Schein, 2002). Structural stability means that the achievement of a group identity is a key culture component which acts as a major stabilising force that will not be given up easily because culture survives even when some members of the organisation depart bearing in mind that it is hard to change since members' value stability as a cause of meaning and reliability. On the other hand, depth means that culture is the deepest, often unconscious part of a group and is hence less tangible and less visible implying that something that is more deeply embedded also lends to stability. Likewise, breadth implies that once culture breadth is developed, it covers all of a group's functioning because culture is pervasive and influences all aspects of how an organisation deals with its primary task, its various environments, and its internal operations.

While patterning/integration is the combining of culture elements into a larger paradigm that causes stability since culture implies that rituals, climate, values, and behaviours tie together into a coherent whole to form a pattern/integration which is referred to as culture. It is from these four elements of structural stability, cultural depth, cultural breadth and patterning/ integration that Schein (1983) developed his theory which emphasizes the three main levels of culture namely artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions. After an extensive study, Hatch (1993) reformulated and improved Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture into the cultural dynamic model involving four elements of culture namely; manifestation, realization, symbolization, and interpretation process. Manifestation refers to any process by which an essence reveals itself usually through the senses but also through cognition and emotion. That is, manifestation contributes to the constitution of organisational culture by translating intangible assumptions into recognisable values manifested in ways of seeing, feeling and knowing within an organisation.

On the other hand, realisation is responsible for the transformation of values into artefacts. In addition, symbolisation is a prospective response that links an artifacts objective form and literal meaning to experiences that lie beyond the literal domain. Cassirer (1946) stated that symbolisation produces reality. While interpretation implies that the meaning of an experience is established retrospectively. Further, by their nature, symbols allow comprehension and provide scope for explanatory tactics by those who utilise them. Schein (1983, 1985, 1992, & 2004) clarified that the level of artifacts is at the surface and it includes all the events that you would see, hear, and feel when you experience a new group with a strange culture. Also, Lehman (2017) reported that artifacts were easily observable in the physical spaces of the organisations, the apparent behaviours of employees, and in how work was organised and done such as participation, attitude to risk, action orientation, power distance and openness. Artifacts include the observable consequences of the group, such as the architecture of its physical environment; its language; its technology and products; its artistic creations; its style, as realised in clothing, styles of demeanour, and emotional manifestations; its folk tells and stories told about the organisation; its disclosed records of values; and its observable customs and ceremonies.

This level of culture is that it is both easily noticeable and very complicated to comprehend (Schein, 2016 & Thompson, 2021). On the other hand, Makumbe and Washaya (2022) explained that values are inner feelings that are rarely debatable and detectable but are exhibited in the behavioural patterns of organisational members (Hofstede, 2011). Values define what is significant in the organisation and what warrants members' attention (Cummings & Worley, 2009). A value is verified only by the collective experience of a group and if it is incorporated, collective, and routine in an organisation it turns into an assumption (Morente et al., 2018). Cultural elements constituted in these levels are cognitive operations, responsibilities and obligations, agreements, ethics, ideologies, policies and strategies, mission, knowledge, and visions (Morente et al., 2018), while basic

assumptions are the taken-for-granted beliefs that dictate how govern how team members perceive, think, and feel about perspectives (Mullins, 2010). Basic assumptions develop as a result of particular solutions that are repeatedly applied until it becomes a standard way of doing things. As basic assumptions imply basic beliefs about aspects it is generally accommodative, indisputable and extremely hard to change (Schein, 2004).

Similarly, basic underlying assumptions reflect the learnings or values of an organisation that have consistently been confirmed to work and are therefore considered the justified way to do things. Ultimately, these beliefs and values that explain the correct way to do things drop out of awareness and become taken for granted assumptions that are the true foundations of the culture. At this level, culture informs organisational members of their status quo, how to treat one another, and how to initiate their self-confidence (Thompson, 2021). Importantly, Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture laid a foundation for the understanding of organisational culture and its complexities. In this case, different scholars (Brenyah & Obuobisa-Darko, 2017; Hogan & Coote, 2014; Martinez et al., 2015) had used Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture. However, the weakness of Schein's Theory was that it emphasised the importance of symbols and values while underestimating other elements of the organisation which might misrepresent the reality of organisations (Hofstede & Bond, 1988). Nevertheless, Schein's Theory identified important cultural aspects in an organisation which were cultural artefacts, espoused values and underlying assumptions that were thus studied in relation to organisational effectiveness.

Theoretically, many definitions of organisational culture exist, however, organisational culture ordinarily refers to the organisational values conveyed through norms, artifacts, and observed in behavioural patterns. The inherent worth of values is to act as collective doctrine ideologies that guide behaviours and put in place a comprehensive framework for organisational standard operating procedures (Schein, 1983; O'Reilly et al., 1991; Schein, 1992; Hatch, 1993; & Hogan & Coote, 2013). For instance, values conveyed by top managers facilitate the innovation process by ingraining acceptable behaviours within an organisation's culture. Values therefore provide a precise mechanism through which top managers can exercise influence (Mumford et al., 2002). By accentuating certain values and by establishing analogous guidelines for appropriate behaviours, managers can begin to establish an organisational culture that has an influential and irresistible influence on employee behaviour, which is a powerful predictor for enhancing organisational effectiveness. This is in congruence with (Ramiah, 2020) who revealed that leaders are important because they give direction, provide motivation and inspire followers to maximise their capabilities to attain organisational goals. Previous research has identified values that are associated with an innovation culture as learning development, participative decision-making, collaborative problem-solving, openness and flexibility, internal communication, cooperation, responsibility, appreciation, and risk-taking (Makumbe and Washaya, 2022).

Scholars such as Homburg and Pflesser (2000), and Hogan and Coote (2014) also established that values have an influence on innovative behaviours which in turn enhance organisational effectiveness. Kunene (2019) investigated the impact of organisational culture on attracting potential employees to work at the organisation. This results concluded that institutions need to portray the appropriate organisational culture to ensure an employee's competence and capability to attract the organisations required performance requirements and align with the leadership needs. This ultimately promotes organisational innovation, productivity and hence effectiveness. However, the organisational culture of administrative and academic heads public universities in Uganda is low manifested by low self-awareness where some university employees quickly resort to strikes rather than dialogue due to frequent disagreements among them, there prevail high rate of absenteeism, tardiness, sabotage, rampant gossip, and rumours (Kato et al., 2024).

A study by Turyahikayo et al., (2024b) conducted in selected public universities in Uganda indicated that a number of university employees simmering conspiracy, disputes and uncertainty resulting from a poor culture of governance, which normally enhances ineffectiveness. On his part, Simpuriiso (2022) revealed that some university employees manifest a poor culture by boasting to students and despising them instead of helping them to realise their academic goals. University leaders have a tradition of conducting themselves in a mode that suggests that they do not care about the development of their followers. For instance, a circular issued to academics by the management of Kyambogo University on July 3, 2022 directed that application for promotion would only take place after internal advertisement. This was followed by another circular on July 20, 2022 specifying that applications for promotion would wait for communication from management to the heads of departments declaring existing vacant positions in a financial year. These pronouncements infringed the human resource manual which reserves the development requirements that comprise of having the necessary qualifications, publications, community service and supervision of graduate students (Turyahikayo et al., 2024c).

The above contextual and empirical evidence seem to suggest that organisational culture of administrative and academic heads in public universities of Uganda is low. Hence, this study tested the measures of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture in the context of administrative and academic heads in selected public universities in Uganda.

The study tested the hypotheses to the effect that:

1. To establish the artifacts of administrative and academic heads of selected public universities.
2. To establish the espoused beliefs and values of administrative and academic heads of selected public universities.
3. To establish the basic underlying assumptions of administrative and academic heads of selected public universities.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

In the early 1980s, organisational culture became a crucial and key concern in the study of organisational behaviour. The culture of an organisation is often a formidable characteristic to define since many elements of culture are intangible and therefore invisible. Despite this hardship, most scholars seem to concur that organisational culture is key to the functioning of an organisation (Khaddour, 2024). Organisational culture change is an essential antecedent for enhancing the successful organisational system implementation. It entails change and transformation of behaviours, attitudes, beliefs, practices, thinking and etiquettes to influence the overall seamless implementation of the organisational planned activities (Okanga, & Adesegeha, 2025). Bogale & Debelo (2024) asserted that organisational culture serves as a foundational set of beliefs shaped by the members of an organisation through external adaptation or internal integration. They further defined it as a collection of fundamental assumptions, norms, values, and shared conduct transmitted to newcomers.

Many researchers (e.g. Morente et al., 2018; Ouellette et al., 2020; Yip et al., 2020) concur that organisational culture embraces a common set of values, behaviours, conventions, attitudes, assumptions, and beliefs among organisational employees. According to Gochhayat et al. (2017), organisational culture means that new members are socialized faster and are quickly brought into coordination with older staff members because of a wider concurrence of beliefs, greater normative pressure and non-conflicting nature of the organisation's goals and practices. Alignment of core values and beliefs obtains a high degree of integration and coordination (Beytekin et al., 2010). Such an alignment between espoused beliefs and actual practices enhances organisation effectiveness. A shared sense of purpose, direction and strategy can foster organisation identification and strengthen organisation members' actions towards organisation vision enhancing organisation effectiveness (Aitken & Treuer, 2021). Therefore, a stronger organisational culture often leads to a higher organisational effectiveness.

The study done on employees of microfinance institutions in Kenya by Owino and Kibera (2019) investigated the influence of organisational culture on performance and the results of hierarchical regression showed that organisational culture had a significant influence on organisational performance. Additionally, the study conducted on employees in the Jordanian banking sector in Jordan by Al-bawaia et al. (2022) investigated the influence of corporate culture on organisational effectiveness. The statistical results revealed a significant influence of corporate culture and three of its dimensions; clan culture, market culture, and hierarchy culture on organisational effectiveness with the fourth -dimension adhocracy culture having no influence on organisational effectiveness. Furthermore, the study conducted in China by Aoki (2020) investigated the impact of material artefacts in managing the learning-performance paradox using employees from two transformation manufacturing plants in a Chinese company to implement continuous improvement. The qualitative findings from both projects indicated that material artefacts triggered social interaction, through which frontline employees were stimulated to focus on both performance and learning. Organizational culture dimensions focus specifically on the culture within organizations. However, all the above studies paused a contextual gap since they were not conducted in Uganda and in non-university environments with differing climates and operating conditions.

According to Bogale and Debelo (2024), different researchers use different dimensions to measure organisational culture. Some studies used beliefs, norms, and workplace interactions to measure organisational culture. For instance, Yip et al. (2020) stated that the basic values of an organization can be viewed as internalized normative beliefs that influence behaviour; Ouellette et al. (2020) stated values and norms are related to group beliefs and customs about the importance of particular behaviours, methods of doing work, and/or how to react to change; Baird et al. (2018) stated that organisational value includes teamwork, innovation, outcome orientation, and attention to detail; Binder (2016) points out values in NPO culture, which include innovation, environmental sustainability, & community service. In addition, Belay et al. (2023) looked at organisational culture in terms of innovation, adaptability, collaboration, and ethical orientation in CSR practices; Ouellette et al. (2020) specified that the interactions between frontline workers and managers, as well as cooperation among co-workers, play a significant role in the development of organisation culture at any organisation; Hussain et al. (2022) also found that interactions between employees and managers foster an innovative culture by contributing to the creation of new ideas, products, and services; Rohim and Budhiasa (2019) confirmed that the interactive organisational culture is positively related to knowledge management and innovation.

Suifan (2021) points out four different sub-systems that can be used to measure organisational culture, including clan (people-oriented, friendly collaboration), hierarchy (process-oriented, structured control), market (results-oriented, competitiveness), and adhocracy (dynamic, entrepreneurial) cultures. Rostain (2021) reported that all of these sub-systems have a positive impact on the entrepreneurial orientation of firms. Shuaib and He (2021) also confirmed that there is a significant association between innovation and organisational culture dimensions, such as adhocracy, clan, market, and hierarchy culture. Moreover, Azeem et al. (2021) also adopted adhocracy, clan, hierarchy, and market dimensions to measure organisational culture. The study found that this culture influences the competitive advantage of organizations. Furthermore, the study also found that this culture encourages workforce innovation, knowledge sharing, and high-level business processes. Bosire and Kinyua (2022) measured organisational culture based on power distance (power, authority, wisdom, and seniority), individualism vs. collectivism (value for achievement, rewarding systems, and individual group relationships), uncertainty avoidance (risk-taking and change), and masculinity (agreeableness, toughness, logical analysis, and quality of life). The study found that job design, decision-making, control structures, and reward systems are among the dimensions of organisational culture.

Schein (1985) conceptualised organisational culture in terms of three levels that must be possessed by effective organisations namely; artefacts, espoused beliefs and values, and underlying assumptions. Artefacts has been measured and defined by various researchers, including (Owino and Kibera, 2019; Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa, 2012; Hogan & Coote, 2013; & Turyahikayo et al., 2024c). The indicators that measure artifacts by Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa (2012) are personal, like a family; entrepreneurial, risk taking; competitive, achievement oriented; controlled and structured,; mentoring, facilitating, nurturing, entrepreneurial, innovative, risk taking; no-nonsense, aggressive, results oriented; coordinating, organizing, efficiency oriented; teamwork, consensus, and participation; individual risk taking, innovation, freedom, and uniqueness; competitiveness and achievement; security, conformity, predictability; organizational glue; loyalty and mutual trust; commitment to innovation, development; emphasis on achievement and goal accomplishment; formal rules and policies; human development, high trust, openness; acquisition of resources, creating new challenges; competitive actions and winning; permanence and stability; development of human resources, teamwork, concern for people; unique and new products and services; winning in the marketplace, outpacing the competition; and dependable, efficient, low cost.

The indicators of artifacts by Hogan & Coote (2013) are; well known stories about employees who have developed new and useful ideas, stories about employees who have strongly encouraged the implementation of new practices and processes, meeting areas and discussion rooms where employees can meet to discuss new ideas and ways to implement them, set aside office layout space where employees can meet and talk informally about new ideas and novel ways to solve problems, effort to celebrate the adoption of new practices and processes, effort to acknowledge and reward the implementation of new services and ways of doing things, get some benefit from looking at this problem from a different perspective, develop a new approach to solving this problem or are there other ways about resolving this issue. Owino and Kibera (2019).developed indicators of measuring artifacts in terms of emphasis on customers and competitors by CEO across departments, departmental heads strive to deliver superior customer value, customer satisfaction is the basis of employee rewards, structural adjustments are carried out to adapt to changes in the market, existence of established effective systems, policies, and guidelines, risks are avoided in business practices, employees embrace teamwork, management creates bonding sessions at least once a year, inputs of every employee is considered in management decision, investment in research and innovation, focus on external environment takes priority over internal orientation, and strategies reviewed from time to time to effectively respond to environmental changes.

The indicators of measuring artifacts by Turyahikayo et al.,(2024c) are; promote cooperation, consensus and group wellbeing, merit is the most important basis for promotion, staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued, the structure is highly centralized i.e. the majority of matters have to pass through very few hands, and constant concern to keep the technology up to date. However, the scholars above have used different indicators of measuring artifacts as the first level of organisational culture basing on the dimensions of culture they used. Turyahikayo et al., (2024c) operationalized organisational culture directly basing on the the three levels of organisational culture. The rest used other dimensions of culture in relation to the levels. Further, Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa (2012) validated organisational culture using a Competing Value Framework where organisational culture was dimensionalised as clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture, and a hierarchy culture where each dimension was categorised in terms of styles from A to D respectively. Hence, despite efforts to assess Schein's Organisational Culture Theory, inconsistencies in the indicators used across studies reveal a gap in standardized measurement. This discrepancy punctuates the necessity of this study to review and confirm the relevance of the indicators in the existing measurement scale. This therefore requires validating current measurement scales to ensure consistency and reliability. Hence, the need for this study.

On the other hand, espoused beliefs and values was validated by many scholars (Hogan & Coote, 2013; Turyahikayo et al., 2024c; & Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa, 2012).The measurement indicators of espoused beliefs and values by Hogan & Coote (2013) are; striving to be successful with new ways of doing things, encouraged to be the most creative and innovative firm in our market, striving to be successful with generating new ideas is expected, open to new ideas and responsive to them, flexible in dealing with new ideas and approach to solving problems, willingness to try new ideas is encouraged, open communication of new ideas and practices is expected to be second nature, information about new ideas and new ways of doing things is expected to be communicated throughout, expecting quality of internal communication related to new ideas and processes to be high, creativity and innovation to be part of the professional skill, expect a high level of competence in developing and implementing new ideas, high levels of knowledge supporting innovation are expected, expect working together to implement new processes,

In addition, encourage team work throughout entire firm in order to develop new ideas and practices, expect working collaboratively in order to implement new ways of doing things, encourage employees to take responsibility for new ways of doing things in their work, expect employees to use their initiative in developing new ideas and ways of dealing with work tasks, take an active role in trying out new ways of doing things, recognizing and rewarding employees who implement new ideas is the norm, taking the time to acknowledge employees' efforts when they solve problems in novel ways is encouraged, appreciating the efforts of employees who bring new practices into being is expected, expect employees to challenge the status quo in order to come up with new ideas and ways of doing things, encourage employees to experiment with new ideas and new ways of solving problems, and taking calculated risks with new ideas and practices is encouraged.

The indicators that measure espoused beliefs and values using the Competing Values Framework by Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa (2012) are personal, like a family; entrepreneurial, risk taking; competitive, achievement oriented; controlled and structured; mentoring, facilitating, nurturing, entrepreneurial, innovative, risk taking; no-nonsense, aggressive, results oriented; coordinating, organizing, efficiency oriented; teamwork, consensus, and participation; individual risk taking, innovation, freedom, and uniqueness; competitiveness and achievement; security, conformity, predictability; organizational glue; loyalty and mutual trust; commitment to innovation, development; emphasis on achievement and goal accomplishment; formal rules and policies; human development, high trust, openness; acquisition of resources, creating new challenges; competitive actions and winning; permanence and stability; development of human resources, teamwork, concern for people; unique and new products and services; winning in the marketplace, outpacing the competition; and dependable, efficient, low cost.

However, this is assumed to be cutting across all culture levels since it is based on different culture dimensions of clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture, and a hierarchy culture. Still, the measurement indicators show some variation which creates confusion among organisational culture scholars, hence need for this theory that validates organisational culture based on its levels. The measurement indicators for Turyahikayo et al., (2024c) are customer service is good, openness and learning are promoted, team work is encouraged, adherence to rules is emphasized, student and staff satisfaction is highly valued, and growth and learning are given value. However, a conceptual gap was observed as different scholars used different dimensions to validate organisational culture creating a discrepancy. This may cause confusion future researchers. Thus, there is need for a standardized tool for better consistency and reliability.

Furthermore, many scholars validated basic underlying assumptions (Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa, 2012; Hogan & Coote, 2013; & Turyahikayo et al., 2024c). The measurement indicators of underlying assumptions by Hogan & Coote (2013) are that value success, aspire to be the best in the market, place great value on our performance, value openness and responsiveness, place great value on being flexible when approaching problems, willingness to show flexibility and openness is valued, open communication is valued, place great value on excellent internal communication, maintaining high quality internal communication is valued, place great value on professional knowledge and skills, aspire to a high level of competence and professionalism, upholding the highest levels of professionalism is valued, cooperation among different work teams is valued highly, values integration and sharing among teams throughout, place great value on co-ordination among different work teams, place great value on every employee being proactive, values employees using their initiative, value employees taking responsibility for their work, place great value on recognizing and rewarding employees' accomplishments, taking time to celebrate employees' work achievements,

Additionally, place great value on showing our appreciation for the efforts of each employee, firm values a willingness to challenge the status quo, values a willingness to experiment with new ideas, and valuing calculated risk-taking helped this firm get to where it is today, the measurement indicators of underlying assumptions by Turyahikayo et al., (2024c) are that mutual responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized, objectives have been communicated to staff, staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making, job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks, encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions, and a trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established. However, studies on underlying assumptions use different indicators, highlighting a need for standardization. This requires validating current measurement scales to ensure consistency and reliability.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Sample

The study used the correlational research design. The correlational research design is a quantitative research design that seeks to ascertain the level of correlation between or among the variables. The design helped to analyse linkages between variables (Mohajan, 2020). The correlational design involved assessing organisational culture levels in the context of administrative and academic heads of public universities in Uganda. The population of the study comprised 265 administrative and academic heads that is 85 people for Kyambogo University, 60 for MUST, 63 for Gulu University and 62 people for Busitema University. Since the population was small, the researchers planned to study all of them based on the table for sample size determination provided by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). However, appropriate data was collected from 231 people comprising 61% the projected study participants after data processing that eliminated missing data and outliers. This sample was considered sufficient because according to Mellahi and Harris (2016) a response rate of 50% above is good in humanity studies. This made it possible to obtain the data required to generalize the study's conclusions.

Instrument

The data collection instrument was a self-administered questionnaire constructed based on an earlier instrument by Schein (1998) who operationalized organisational culture in terms of the three main levels of artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions. The indicators of artefacts are promote cooperation, consensus and group wellbeing, merit is the most important basis for promotion, staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued, the structure is highly centralized i.e. the majority of matters have to pass through very few hands, and constant concern to keep the technology up to date. On the other hand, the indicators of espoused beliefs and values are customer service is good, openness and learning are promoted, team work is

encouraged, adherence to rules is emphasized, student and staff satisfaction is highly valued, and growth and learning are given value. While the indicators for basic underlying assumptions are mutual responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized, objectives have been communicated to staff, staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making, job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks, encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions, and a trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established. Before data collection, factor analysis using smartPLS was utilised to validate the instrument at the preliminary level. The indicators in each dimension were scaled using a five-point Likert scale, with one representing the worst-case scenario and five representing the best-case scenario. The anchors used were 1=Strongly Disagreed (SD), 2= Disagreed (D), 3= Not Sure (NS), 4=Agreed (A), and 5 = Strongly Agreed (SA).

Data Analysis

The data analysis included computing descriptive statistics in terms of frequencies and percentages for the public universities’ heads of administrative and academic staffs' background characteristics. SmartPLS was used to create measurement models that ensured their validity and reliability. The measurement models included a validity and reliability test. Validity testing included calculating the Heterotriat-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlation and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) to determine whether the measure indicators were consistent and independent. Reliability tests involved Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). In addition to Cronbach's Alpha, CR was tested since it allows indicators of variables to become reliable. Further, CR takes into account the external properties of the indicator variables. Partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was used to create the model that shows relevant indicators for the several components of Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture.

Findings

This section shows the results for organisational culture in the context of administrative and academic heads in selected in public universities in Uganda. The results include demographic profiles of both the administrative and academic heads that participated in the study, the measurement methods and the structural models.

Demographic Profiles of the Respondents

Demographical profiles were considered in terms of sex, age categories, education levels and working experience. The results on the same were as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of administrative and academic heads

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	152	65.0
	Female	82	35.0
	Total	234	100.0
Age Groups	Up to 30	6	2.6
	30 but below 40	45	19.2
	40 and above	183	78.2
	Total	234	100.0
Highest academic qualification	Bachelor’s degree	18	7.7
	Masters	101	43.2
	PhD	115	49.1
	Total	234	100.0
Working Experience	Less than one year	30	12.8
	1 but less than 5 years	41	17.5
	5 but less than 10 years	63	26.9
	More than 10 years	100	42.7
	Total	234	100.0

The results in Table 1 on gender indicate that males (65.0%) were the relatively larger number of administrative and academic heads who offered the responses while the females were the least group (35.0%). Thus, the findings reveal that a bigger number of male administrative and academic heads participated in this study. Nevertheless, both male and female administrative and academic heads were considered for the study since the population of female heads was equally high. The majority of the study participants (78.2%) were 40 years and above with 19.2% aged between 30-40 years and 2.6% aged 30 years and below. Thus, results were representative of administrative and academic heads covering all age groups. The modal percentage (49.1%) was of those with PhD degrees followed by 43.2% who had master’s degrees, and 7.7 % had bachelor’s degrees. Thus, results are generalizable to academic staff with different academic qualifications at university occupying different administrative and academic positions of leadership. Further, the modal percentage (42.7 %) was of those who had served for 10 years and above followed by 26.9% who had served between 5-10 years, 17.5% had served between 1-5 years, and 12.8% had served for less than 1 year. Thus, the results report that administrative

and academic heads who participated in the study had spent a substantial period of time serving the universities. Thus, the findings can be generalised on different academic and administrative heads in the universities.

Measurement Models

The measurement models include discriminant validity (Heterotrait-monotrait ratio Correlations (HTMT)), reliability (Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliabilities), average variance extracted, and Collinearity assessment. Discriminant validity measured the independence of the measures (constructs) while Cronbach’s alpha (α) and composite reliability (CR) measuring a construct (Cheung et al., 2023). The results follow in Tables 2 and 3

Table 2. AVE and Heterotrait Monotrait (HTMT) Discriminant Validity assessment

Measures	AVE	IC	EV	UA
IC				
EV	0.671	0.829		
UA	0.768	0.477	0.855	

EV = Espoused beliefs and values, IC = Institutional Culture, UA = Underlying assumptions

The convergent validity results in terms of average variance extracted (AVE) indicated that all AVE values were above the minimum of 0.5 and heterotrait–monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations were all below the maximum 0.90 (Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021) indicating validity of the instrument. Therefore, with AVE values above the minimum, the constructs measuring the different variable converged on them hence were appropriate measures while with heterotrait–monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations also below the minimum, the constructs were independent measures hence discriminatingly valid.

Table 3. Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha for the Study Constructs

Measures	α	CR
Adaptability	0.775	0.847
Flexibility	0.721	0.827
Productivity	0.762	0.840
Espoused beliefs and values	0.756	0.860
Underlying assumptions	0.698	0.869

Source: Survey data (2023)

The reliability results in Table 3 indicated that the Cronbach’s (save for construct of underlying assumptions with $\alpha = .698$) and composite reliability values were the minimum of 0.70 for both (Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021). That meant that the indicators of the different measures (constructs) measuring the variables were reliable. Therefore, the indicators of the different measures were interrelated or highly correlated hence the data collected was reliable. However, the construct of message characteristics did not attain the reliability and therefore, it was dropped from the subsequent analysis. Since Cronbach Alpha has limitations of presuming that all indicator features are the same in the study population, therefore decreasing the reliability scores. In addition, Cronbach's Alpha is sensitive to the number of items on the scale and often underestimates the reliability of internal consistency (Hair Jr. et al., 2021). However, composite reliability is liberal since it takes into account the external properties of the indicator variables (Fu et al., 2022). Further, the Collinearity (VIF) test demonstrated that there was no high correlation (collinearity) between the constructs that measured Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture because the results were less than 5, which is the maximum (Tomaschek et al., 2018). The VIF results indicated that the constructs used to measure Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture were independent, and hence measured the theory independently.

Structural Model for Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture

Structural equation modelling was used to determine the Transformational-Transactional Leadership Theory measures. Figure 1 displays the results. The structural model showed the indicators of the different constructs measuring the variable.

Figure 1: Structural model for Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture

Source: Survey data (2024)

The figure 1 indicated that organisational culture was investigated as a bi-dimensional concept that included the espoused beliefs and values and the basic underlying assumptions. The third construct namely artefacts was removed during the outlier analysis because all of its five indicators (IF1-IF5) were less than 0.50 as the minimum validity value during the factor analysis. Similarly, all of the indicators for artefacts did not load highly above 0.50 and were removed. For the espoused beliefs and values, three indicators (EV2-EV4) out of the six measuring it loaded highly above the 0.50 which was the minimum validity value when using the factor analysis as was recommended by Hair Jr et al (2021) and were thus retained but the three indicators (EV1, EV5 & EV6) did not load and were dropped. For the basic underlying assumptions, only two (UA1 &UA3) out of the six indicators measuring it loaded highly but four of the indicators (UA2, UA4, UA5 &UA6) did not load and were removed at the outlier analysis stage. For that matter, the retained indicators were valid measures of the constructs in the model.

DISCUSSION

The results revealed that the two out of the three constructs of espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions save for artefacts were appropriate measures of the Schein’s Theory of Organisational Culture. For example, artefacts, emphasis on customers and competitors across departments, departmental heads strive to deliver superior customer value, customer satisfaction is the basis of employee rewards, structural adjustments are carried out to adapt to changes in the market, existence of established effective systems, policies, and guidelines, risks are avoided in business practices, employees embrace teamwork, management creates bonding sessions at least once a year, inputs of every employee is considered in management decision, investment in research and innovation, focus on external environment takes priority over internal orientation, and strategies reviewed from time to time to effectively respond to environmental changes (Owino and Kibera, 2019).

Further, personal, like a family; entrepreneurial, risk taking; competitive, achievement oriented; controlled and structured; mentoring, facilitating, nurturing, entrepreneurial, innovative, risk taking; no-nonsense, aggressive, results oriented; coordinating, organizing, efficiency oriented; teamwork, consensus, and participation; individual risk taking, innovation, freedom, and uniqueness; competitiveness and achievement; security, conformity, predictability; organizational glue; loyalty and mutual trust; commitment to innovation, development; emphasis on achievement and goal accomplishment; formal rules and policies; human development, high trust, openness; acquisition of resources, creating new challenges; competitive actions and winning; permanence and stability; development of human resources, teamwork, concern for people; unique and new products and services; winning in the marketplace, outpacing the competition; and dependable, efficient, low cost (Ng’ang’a & Nyongesa ,2012).

Additionally, well known stories about employees who have developed new and useful ideas, stories about employees who have strongly encouraged the implementation of new practices and processes, meeting areas and discussion rooms where employees can meet to discuss new ideas and ways to implement them, set aside office layout space where employees can meet and talk informally about new ideas and novel ways to solve problems, effort to celebrate the adoption of new practices and processes, effort to acknowledge and reward the implementation of new services and ways of doing things, get some benefit from looking at this problem from a different perspective, develop a new approach to solving this problem or are there other ways about resolving this issue (Hogan &Coote, 2013), promote cooperation, consensus and group wellbeing, merit is the most important basis for promotion, staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued, the structure is highly centralized i.e. the majority of matters have to pass through very few hands, and constant concern to keep the technology up to date (Turyahikayo et.,2024c). With the

current consistent with the previous measurement scales, it can be affirmed that the indicators studied were valid measures of artifacts.

For espoused beliefs and values, it was confirmed that the indicators measured the construct consistent with the previous researchers. As such, the study indicated that personal, like a family; entrepreneurial, risk taking; competitive, achievement oriented; controlled and structured; mentoring, facilitating, nurturing, entrepreneurial, innovative, risk taking; no-nonsense, aggressive, results oriented; coordinating, organizing, efficiency oriented; teamwork, consensus, and participation; individual risk taking, innovation, freedom, and uniqueness; competitiveness and achievement; security, conformity, predictability; organizational glue; loyalty and mutual trust; commitment to innovation, development; emphasis on achievement and goal accomplishment; formal rules and policies; human development, high trust, openness; acquisition of resources, creating new challenges; competitive actions and winning; permanence and stability; development of human resources, teamwork, concern for people; unique and new products and services; winning in the marketplace, outpacing the competition; and dependable, efficient, low cost (Ng'ang'a & Nyongesa, 2012), striving to be successful with new ways of doing things, encouraged to be the most creative and innovative firm in our market, striving to be successful with generating new ideas is expected, open to new ideas and responsive to them, flexible in dealing with new ideas and approach to solving problems.

In addition, willingness to try new ideas is encouraged, open communication of new ideas and practices is expected to be second nature, information about new ideas and new ways of doing things is expected to be communicated throughout, expecting quality of internal communication related to new ideas and processes to be high, creativity and innovation to be part of the professional skill, expect a high level of competence in developing and implementing new ideas, high levels of knowledge supporting innovation are expected, expect working together to implement new processes, encourage team work throughout entire firm in order to develop new ideas and practices, expect working collaboratively in order to implement new ways of doing things, encourage employees to take responsibility for new ways of doing things in their work, expect employees to use their initiative in developing new ideas and ways of dealing with work tasks, take an active role in trying out new ways of doing things, recognizing and rewarding employees who implement new ideas is the norm, taking the time to acknowledge employees' efforts when they solve problems in novel ways is encouraged, appreciating the efforts of employees who bring new practices into being is expected, expect employees to challenge the status quo in order to come up with new ideas and ways of doing things, encourage employees to experiment with new ideas and new ways of solving problems, and taking calculated risks with new ideas and practices is encouraged (Hogan & Coote, 2013), customer service is good, openness and learning are promoted, team work is encouraged, adherence to rules is emphasized, student and staff satisfaction is highly valued, and growth and learning are given value. (Turyahikayo et al., 2024c). With the current consistent with the previous measurement scales, it can be affirmed that the indicators studied were valid measures of espoused beliefs and values.

For basic underlying assumptions, it was confirmed that the indicators measured the construct consistent with the previous researchers. As such, the study indicated that value success, aspire to be the best in the market, place great value on our performance, value openness and responsiveness, place great value on being flexible when approaching problems, willingness to show flexibility and openness is valued, open communication is valued, place great value on excellent internal communication, maintaining high quality internal communication is valued, place great value on professional knowledge and skills, aspire to a high level of competence and professionalism, upholding the highest levels of professionalism is valued, cooperation among different work teams is valued highly, values integration and sharing among teams throughout, place great value on co-ordination among different work teams, place great value on every employee being proactive, values employees using their initiative, value employees taking responsibility for their work, place great value on recognizing and rewarding employees' accomplishments, taking time to celebrate employees' work achievements, place great value on showing our appreciation for the efforts of each employee, firm values a willingness to challenge the status quo, values a willingness to experiment with new ideas, and valuing calculated risk-taking helped this firm get to where it is today (Hogan & Coote (2013), mutual responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized, objectives have been communicated to staff, staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making, job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks, encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions, and a trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established (Turyahikayo et al., 2024c). The results align with earlier research, confirming that the indicators examined accurately reflect basic underlying, thereby validating their use as effective measurement tools.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that indicators assessed in this article to measure Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture, namely artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions are valid and reliable. For artifacts, the indicators are promote cooperation, consensus and group wellbeing, merit is the most important basis for promotion, staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued, the structure is highly centralized i.e. the majority of matters have to pass through very few hands, and constant concern to keep the technology up to date. For espoused beliefs and values, customer service is good, openness and learning are promoted, team work is encouraged, adherence to rules is emphasized, student and staff satisfaction is highly valued, and growth and learning are given value while for basic underlying assumptions the indicators are that mutual responsibility and shared

objectives are emphasized, objectives have been communicated to staff, staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making, job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks, encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions, and a trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends that researchers can use the indicators assessed in this article to measure the three elements of Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture, namely artifacts, espoused beliefs and values, and basic underlying assumptions. These indicators have been tested and validated, providing a robust framework for scholars to investigate Schein's Theory of Organisational Culture in various contexts. By using these indicators, researchers can confidently explore how these different elements of organisational culture influence different behavioural variables. For artifacts the indicators include promote cooperation, consensus and group wellbeing, merit is the most important basis for promotion, staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued, the structure is highly centralized i.e. the majority of matters have to pass through very few hands, and constant concern to keep the technology up to date. For espoused beliefs and values the indicators are customer service is good, openness and learning are promoted, team work is encouraged, adherence to rules is emphasized, student and staff satisfaction is highly valued, and growth and learning are given value while for basic underlying assumptions the indicators are that mutual responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized, objectives have been communicated to staff, staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making, job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks, encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions, and a trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Instrument

Construct	Item	Measure
Section A: organisational culture		
Artefacts (OA)	OA1	Promote cooperation, consensus and group well being
	OA2	Merit is the most important for promotion
	OA3	Staff creativeness and innovativeness are highly valued
	OA.4	Structure is highly centralised i.e the majority of matters have to pass through very hand
	OA.5	Constant concern to keep technology up to date.
Esposued values. (EV)	EV.1	Customer service is good.
	EV.2	Openness and learning are promoted
	EV.3	Team work is encouraged
	EV.4	Adherence to rules is emphasized
	EV.5	Student and staff satisfaction is highly valued
	EV.6	Growth and learning are given values
Underlying Assumptions (UA)	UA.1	Mutual responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized
	UA.2	Objectives have been communicated to staff
	UA.3	Staff members are encouraged to participate in decision making
	UA.4	Job is enriched in terms of adding more meaningful tasks
	UA.5	Encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions
	UA.6	A trusting relationship between supervisors and subordinates has been established